

UNRAVELING THE DYNAMICS OF FISHING BAN: POLICY IMPLEMENTATION AND ECOSYSTEM RESPONSE IN PRES. MANUEL A. ROXAS, ZAMBOANGA DEL NORTE

Felbert C. Falconite ¹, Lynard S. Bulat-Ag ¹, Ian Lister G. Atis ¹
and Diove E. Tabiliran, MAGS ²

¹College of Criminal Justice Education, Jose Rizal Memorial State University – Katipunan Campus, Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines

²College of Teacher Education, Jose Rizal Memorial State University – Katipunan Campus, Katipunan, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

Given that fish is a crucial component of the Filipino diet, fisheries play a significant role in the lives of over one million Filipinos residing in coastal regions. The administration of fisheries in the Philippines has persistent difficulties, which are worsened by the increasingly deteriorating environmental conditions of several coastal habitats. The fisheries in the Philippines are under danger and need effective management. The fisheries in the Philippines have seen significant advantages, but their integrity is now under risk due to decades of inadequate management. This study assessed the implementation of Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, also known as the Fishing Ban Ordinance, of the municipality of Manuel A. Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte in line with policy implementation and eco-system responses of the aforesaid municipality, during Fiscal Year 2024. The gathered data was statistically treated using frequency count, weighted mean, standard deviation, Mann-Whitney U-test and Kruskal-Wallis H-test. The study surveyed respondents aged 39-48, mostly male, elementary/graduate, married, and fishing for over 25 years. The majority favored prohibiting overfishing and fishing during close season, with a mean of 2.88 verbally interpreted as Observed. The majority favored ensuring sustainable and equitable utilization of coastal and marine resources, with a mean of 3.05 verbally interpreted as Moderate. There was a significant relationship between the level of implementation and the perceived effect of the ordinance. However, there was no significant difference in the perceived effect when respondents were

grouped according to age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and number of years fishing.

Keywords: *Coastal, Eco-System, Fishing Ban Policy, Marine Resources, Ordinance*

INTRODUCTION

Given that fish is a crucial component of the Filipino diet, fisheries play a significant role in the lives of over one million Filipinos residing in coastal regions. The administration of fisheries in the Philippines has persistent difficulties, which are worsened by the increasingly deteriorating environmental conditions of several coastal habitats. The fisheries in the Philippines are under danger and need effective management. The fisheries in the Philippines have seen significant advantages, but their integrity is now under risk due to decades of inadequate management. Fisheries provide a substantial contribution to the country's revenue, employment, foreign currency earnings, and nutrition, hence enhancing the country's security. Nevertheless, the advantages are progressively diminishing as a result of diminishing fish harvest, deterioration of habitats, and a growing population reliant on these resources (Tahiluddin & Sarri, 2022).

Accordingly, there are two types of fisheries in the Philippines: the municipal fisheries and the commercial fisheries. Existing law categorizes these two fisheries in a simplistic manner: municipal fisheries refers to fishing activities that use fishing vessels of three (3) gross tons or less or none at all, while commercial fishing uses vessels greater than three (3) gross tons. Municipal fisheries are regulated by local government, while commercial fisheries are regulated by the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources of the Department of Agriculture (DA-BFAR). In addition, a 15-kilometer expanse of waters has been classified as "municipal waters," falling under the jurisdiction of local and city governments. Commercial fishing is not allowed in municipal waters unless special ordinances approving this activity are approved by the municipal or city councils (Terry & Donato, 2024).

Imposing fishing prohibitions is an essential element of the Philippines' approach to encourage sustainable fishing practices. These prohibitions often focus on certain species during their reproductive periods or are enforced in specific regions recognized for their ecological significance. Through the implementation of fishing restrictions during crucial seasons or in locations that are susceptible to damage, these prohibitions aid in the prevention of excessive fishing and facilitate the restoration and replenishment of fish populations. For instance, sardine fishing is temporarily prohibited during certain seasons to safeguard the gatherings of spawning fish, so guaranteeing effective reproduction and the maintenance of robust population levels (Macusi et al., 2021).

Fishing bans and sustainable practices are crucial for long-term ecological health, but they can also cause short-term challenges for fishing communities. Restrictions may lead to reduced income and food insecurity for fisherfolk who rely heavily on daily catches. To address these issues, the government and non-governmental organizations have

implemented support programs, such as aquaculture, eco-tourism, and seaweed farming, as well as financial assistance and capacity-building programs. Education and community involvement are essential for promoting sustainable fishing practices. Raising awareness about marine conservation and sustainable fishing helps garner support and compliance from local communities. Environmental education programs, workshops, and training sessions equip fisherfolk with the knowledge and skills needed to adopt sustainable practices. Involving communities in decision-making processes ensures policies are tailored to local contexts and that fisherfolk feel valued and respected. The implementation of sustainable fishing practices and bans has led to positive environmental outcomes in the Philippines, such as improved biodiversity and fish biomass in marine protected areas, and recovery and restoration of critical habitats like coral reefs, mangroves, and seagrass beds (Tolentino-Zondervan & Zondervan, 2022).

Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014 was implemented to ensure the sustainable management, development, conservation, and preservation of the municipal waterways, fisheries, and aquatic resources, as well as to serve other reasons. The Ordinance will be enforced in all municipal waters as defined by the ordinance, including all fisheries resources within those waters. It applies to all activities, businesses, and entities involved in the use, development, conservation, and management of the municipal waters and its coastal and fisheries resources. This includes all individuals, entities, or corporations that currently use or plan to use the coastal and fishery resources of the municipality (Municipality of Pres. Manuel Roxas, 2014). Therefore, the researchers This study assessed the implementation of Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, also known as the Fishing Ban Ordinance, of the municipality of Manuel A. Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte in line with policy implementation and eco-system responses of the aforesaid municipality, during Fiscal Year 2024. Additionally, this aligns with the investigation of the effects of a fishing ban on sustainability by evaluating the enforcement of the specific regulation and its impact on the ecosystem of the town.

Research Questions

This study assessed the implementation of Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, also known as the Fishing Ban Ordinance, of the municipality of Manuel A. Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte in line with policy implementation and eco-system responses of the aforesaid municipality, during Fiscal Year 2024.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. Age; and
 - 1.2. Socio-Economic Status;
 - 1.2.1. Gender;
 - 1.2.2. Educational Attainment;
 - 1.2.3. Civil Status; and
 - 1.2.4. Number of Years Fishing?

2. What is the level of implementation of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014 in the municipality of Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte?
3. What is the perceived effect of the implementation of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014 in the municipality of Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation and the perceived effect of the implementation of the Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014 in the municipality of Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte?
5. Is there a significant difference between the perceived effect of the implementation of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014 in the municipality of Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte when respondents were grouped according to their profile?

METHODOLOGY

The researchers used the descriptive method in gathering data. Likewise, the researchers conducted an informal interview with the respondents to determine the veracity and authenticity of the information taken/gathered. It is noteworthy that a descriptive survey method attempts to establish the range and distribution of some social characteristics and discover how these characteristics may be related to certain behavior patterns or attitudes. Further, this study was conducted at the municipality of Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte, focusing on the coastal barangays of the aforementioned municipality, namely, Lower Irasan, Langatian, Nabilid, and Piao. In that line, the researchers selected twenty (20) per barangay; thus, the study had a total of eighty (80) respondents.

Furthermore, the instrument used in this study was a self-made questionnaire that was validated by experts and underwent a reliability test, which yielded a Cronbach-Alpha value of 0.7246. In that line, the researchers personally administered the questionnaire and collected it after the respondents had completed their answers. The retrieved questionnaires were tallied and calculated statistically. Thus, this study used frequency count and percentage computation, weighted mean, Kruskal-Wallis H-test, Mann-Whitney U-test, and Spearman Correlation Coefficient as the statistical formulas used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the responses of the eighty (80) randomly selected fisher folks of the coastal barangays of the municipality of Roxas, Zamboanga del Norte. The responses were treated statistically in order to answer the statement of the problem of the present investigation.

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The data pointed out that most of the respondents were within the age bracket of 39–48 years old, comprising 23 out of 80 respondents, or 28.75%, followed by those respondents who were within the age range of 18–28 years old, comprising 19 out of 80 respondents, or 23.75%, as

compared to those respondents who were above 58 years old, comprising 5 out of 80 respondents, or 6.25%, which implies that most of the fisherfolk in the municipality of Roxas were mature adults. In support, Pimentel et al. (2025) and Enema and Quezon (2024) point out that fishing communities in the Philippines rely on matured adults due to physical demands and environmental changes. The average age of small-scale fishers is 30-50 years, balancing productivity and experience. Younger generations seek alternative livelihoods due to declining fish stocks, seasonal bans, and climate change. Targeted interventions for mature adults, such as skills enhancement and livelihood diversification programs, are crucial for long-term sustainability.

Table 1 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18 – 28 years old	19	23.75%
29 – 38 years old	16	20.00%
39 – 48 years old	23	28.75%
49 – 58 years old	17	21.25%
Above 58 years old	5	6.25%
Total	80	100.00%

Table 2 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. The data pointed out that most of the respondents were males, comprising 69 out of 80 respondents, or 86.25%, as compared to female respondents, comprising 11 out of 80 respondents, or 13.75%, which implies that most of the fisherfolk in the municipality of Roxas were males. In support, Antonio et al. (2025) point to the fact that the majority of fisherfolk are males, reflecting a gender distribution in fishing communities across the Philippines. Fishing is traditionally seen as physically demanding, leading to men dominating the sector. Women contribute to post-harvest activities like fish processing and marketing. This gendered dynamic is crucial for designing inclusive policies that consider both men's and women's contributions to the fishing sector, ensuring equitable access to resources, training, and support programs.

Table 2 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	69	86.25%
Female	11	13.75%
Total	80	100.00%

Table 3 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of educational attainment. The data pointed out that most of the respondents were elementary level/graduates, comprising 41 out of 80 respondents, or 51.25%, followed by those respondents who were high school level or graduates, comprising 28 out of 80

respondents, or 35.00%, as compared to those who were bachelor’s degree holders, comprising 2 out of 80 respondents, or 2.50%, which implies that most of the fisherfolk in the municipality of Roxas were lowly educated. In support, Beldia (2024) states that the Philippines’ small-scale fisherfolk are often lowly educated, reflecting a trend in many fishing communities. This is due to economic constraints, geographic isolation, and cultural norms that prioritize labor in fishing over schooling. The lack of formal education limits access to alternative livelihoods, training programs, and decision-making processes for fisheries management. Government and non-governmental organizations should invest in capacity-building initiatives, adult education programs, and livelihood diversification opportunities to improve the socio-economic conditions of fishing communities.

Table 3 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary Level/Graduate	41	51.25%
High School Level/Graduate	28	35.00%
Post-Secondary Level/Graduate	3	3.75%
College Level	6	7.50%
Bachelor’s Degree Holder	2	2.50%
Total	80	100.00%

Table 4 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of civil status. The data pointed out that most of the respondents were married comprising 56 out of 80 respondents or 70.00% followed by those respondents who were single comprising 16 out of 80 respondents or 20.00% as compared to those who were widow/er comprising 8 out of 80 respondents or 10.00% which implies that most of the fisher folks in the municipality of Roxas were married. In support, Aguinaldo and Gomez (2023) pointed out that most fisherfolks are married, reflecting the trend in Philippine fishing communities. Marriage and family life are crucial for traditional occupations like fishing, where support systems help manage income and work. Married fishers are responsible and committed, actively participating in community-based resource management programs.

Table 4 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	16	20.00%
Married	56	70.00%
Widow/er	8	10.00%
Total	80	100.00%

Table 5 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of their number of years of fishing. The data pointed out that most of the respondents had been fishing for more than 25 years, comprising 25 out of 80 respondents, or 31.25%, followed by those respondents who had been fishing for more than 20 years but less than 25 years, comprising 17 out of 80 respondents, or 21.25%, as compared to those who had been fishing for more than 1 year but less than 5 years, comprising 2 out of 80 respondents, or 2.50%, which implies that the majority of the fisherfolk in the municipality of Roxas were experienced fishermen. In support, Tad-o et al. (2023) pointed out that fishing is a generational skill passed down through generations, fostering traditional ecological knowledge. Small-scale fishers have decades of experience, adapting to seasonal variations and challenging sea conditions.

Table 5 Profile of the Respondents in terms of Number of Years in Fishing

Years in Fishing	Frequency	Percentage
More than 1 year but less than 5 years	2	2.50%
More than 5 years but less than 10 years	14	17.50%
More than 10 years but less than 15 years	11	13.75%
More than 15 years but less than 20 years	11	13.75%
More than 20 years but less than 25 years	17	21.25%
More than 25 years	25	31.25%
Total	80	100.00%

Table 6 Level of Implementation of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014

Level of Implementation of M.O. No. 35, S. 2014	Mean	Interpretation
1. Prohibited fishing gears and fishing outfits seen detrimental to the municipal waters.	2.34	Less Observed
2. Prohibited unauthorized fishing or engaging in other unauthorized fishing activities.	2.76	Observed
3. Declared unlawful the use of fine mesh net.	2.58	Less Observed
4. Declared unlawful fishing through explosive noxious or poisonous substance and/or electricity.	2.43	Less Observed
5. Ban on coral exploitation and exportation.	2.80	Observed
6. Ban muro-ami and other methods and gears destructive to coral reefs and other marine habitat.	2.78	Observed
7. Prohibits the conversion of mangroves.	2.71	Observed
8. Ban the gathering, sell or export white sand, silica, pebbles and any other substance that	2.67	Observed

make up any marine habitat for commercial purposes.		
9. Illegal use of superlight or engage in fishing using superlight.	2.74	Observed
10. Prohibited overfishing and fishing on close season.	2.88	Observed
Average Weighted Mean	2.67	Observed

Legend: 5 - 4.21 - 5.00 - Very Much Observed; 4 - 3.41 - 4.20 - Much Observed; 3 - 2.61 - 3.40 - Observed; 2 - 1.81 - 2.60 - Less Observed; 1 - 1.00 - 1.80 - Not Observed

Table 6 illustrates the extent of execution of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. The data indicated that the majority of respondents preferred the prohibition of overfishing and fishing during closed seasons, with a mean score of 2.88, interpreted as "observed." In contrast, the use of prohibited fishing gear and outfits was deemed detrimental to municipal waters, yielding a mean score of 2.34, interpreted as "less observed." The average weighted mean for this facet is 2.67, which is verbally rendered as "observed." The data indicated that the majority of respondents preferred a ban on overfishing and fishing during closed seasons, suggesting that the enforcement of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, mostly emphasizes the prohibition of overfishing and fishing during closed or off seasons. The results were corroborated by Bagsit et al. (2021), asserting that rules against overfishing and fishing during closed or off-seasons were established due to their impact on livelihoods. However, it significantly impacts the sustainability of resources once thought to be inexhaustible but which are, in fact, diminishing. Further, overfishing is a global phenomenon and a significant concern on an international scale. Irresponsible and excessive fishing practices have resulted in overfishing, potentially adversely affecting impoverished fishing communities.

Table 7 Perceived Effect of Implementation of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014

Effect of the Implementation of M.O. No. 35, S. 2014	Mean	Interpretation
1. Promote conservation of marine resources.	2.62	Moderate
2. Ensure sustainable and equitable utilization of coastal and marine resources.	3.05	Moderate
3. Protect the rights of small and marginal fishers in the preferential use of communal coastal and fishery resources.	2.81	Moderate
4. Allow people's full and active participation in the conservation and management of the coastal and fishery resources.	2.74	Moderate
5. Promote precautionary principle of conservation.	2.87	Moderate
6. Promote awareness of sustainable fishing.	2.58	Low
7. Promote management on the exploitation of living coastal and fishery resources.	2.91	Moderate

8. Provide appropriate technology for the used of the coastal/marine resources.	2.86	Moderate
9. Maintain a sound ecological balance.	2.97	Moderate
10. Protect and enhance the quality of the coastal/marine environment.	2.83	Moderate
Average Weighted Mean	2.83	Moderate

Legend: 5 - 4.21 - 5.00 - Very High; 4 - 3.41 - 4.20 - High; 3 - 2.61 - 3.40 - Moderate; 2 - 1.81 - 2.60 - Low; 1 - 1.00 - 1.80 - Very Low

Table 7 illustrates the perceived impact of the enactment of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, Series of 2014. The findings indicated that the majority of respondents preferred ensuring sustainable and equitable usage of coastal and marine resources, with a mean score of 3.05, evaluated as Moderate, in contrast to promoting awareness of sustainable fishing, which had a mean score of 2.58, read as Low. The average weighted mean for this facet is 2.83, which is vocally evaluated as moderate. The findings emphasized that the majority of respondents supported the sustainable and equitable use of coastal and marine resources, indicating that the implementation of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014 signifies the promotion of such utilization. The results were corroborated by Sin et al. (2024), highlighting that the consistent and stringent enforcement of fishing regulations leads to enhanced sustainability of fishery resources and the regeneration of depleted fish stocks.

Table 8 Relationship Between The Level of Implementation and the Perceived Effect of the Implementation of M.O. No. 35, S. 2014

Variable	Mean	n	α	Cri r _s	Comp r _s	Action
Level of Implementation vs Effect of Implementation	2.6662 2.8242	80	0.05	0.1850	0.6382	Ho Rejected

Table 8 illustrates the correlation between the degree of implementation and the perceived impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. The application of the Spearman Rank Order Coefficient of Correlation produced a computed r that exceeds the critical r, indicating the rejection of the hypothesis asserting a significant relationship between the level of implementation and the perceived effects of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. The results were corroborated by Kumar et al. (2020), highlighting the robust relationship between fisheries governance, sustainable development, and the role of subsidies as an impediment to achieving sustainability objectives. Subsidies resulting in overcapacity and overfishing are said to be "harmful," "detrimental," or "capacity-enhancing." Additionally, established a robust correlation between legislation governing overfishing and the enhancement of aquatic resources.

Table 9 Difference Between the Perceived Effect of the Implementation of M.O. No. 35, s. 2014 when Respondents were grouped According to Age

Age	Mean	df	α	Crit x^2	Comp H	Action
18 – 28 years old	3.0053	4	0.05	9.488	4.437	Ho Accepted
29 – 38 years old	2.7889					
39 – 48 years old	2.7406					
49 – 58 years old	2.7928					
Above 58 years old	2.7400					

Table 9 illustrates the disparity in the perceived impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, based on the respondents' age groups. The application of the Kruskal-Wallis H-test produced a computed H value that was lower than the critical chi-square value, indicating acceptance of the hypothesis asserting no significant difference in the perceived effects of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014 among respondents categorized by age. Consequently, it may be interpreted that both young and elderly fishermen had a similar perspective about the impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. In support, Singh et al. (2024) indicate that capture fisheries have traditionally played a significant role in the economies of coastal or island regions, especially in developing nations; however, there are growing concerns regarding the overexploitation of vital fish stocks and the sustainability of the industry. To combine short-term economic benefits, resource protection, and fisheries sustainability, fisheries management and policymaking must recognize the diverse economic contributions of various fish harvesters to justify and control existing fishing methods more effectively. Consequently, it is evident that the impact of enacting a regulatory rule significantly exceeds an individual's social and economic profile, since it typically affects all individuals.

Table 10 Difference Between the Perceived Effect of the Implementation of M.O. No. 35, s. 2014 when Respondents were grouped According to Gender

Gender	Mean	df	α	Cri U	Comp U	Action
Male	2.8214	67	0.05	229.0	346.00	Ho Accepted
Female	2.8000	11			391.00	

Table 10 illustrates the disparity in the perceived impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, based on the respondents' gender classification. The application of the Wilcoxon Rank-Sum U-test resulted in a computed U value exceeding the critical U value, indicating acceptance of the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the perceived effect of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014 when respondents are categorized by gender. Consequently, it may be inferred that both male and female fishermen had the same perceptions about the impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. The results were corroborated by Ullah et al. (2024), indicating that the impact of

implementing a regulatory rule significantly transcends an individual's social and economic profile, since it typically affects all individuals.

Table 11 Difference Between the Perceived Effect of the Implementation of M.O. No. 35, s. 2014 when Respondents were grouped According to Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Mean	df	α	Crit x^2	Comp H	Action
Elementary Level/Graduate	2.8688	2	0.05	5.991	3.815	Ho Accepted
High School Level/Graduate	2.8325					
College Level	2.6364					

Table 11 illustrates the disparity in the perceived impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, based on the respondents' educational level. The application of the Kruskal-Wallis H-test resulted in a computed H value that was lower than the critical chi-square value, indicating acceptance of the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the perceived effects of the implementation of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, when respondents are categorized by educational attainment. Consequently, it may be inferred that both poorly and highly educated fishermen had the same perspective about the impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. The results were corroborated by Ullah et al. (2024) and Singh et al. (2024), indicating that the impact of implementing a regulatory rule significantly transcends an individual's social and economic profile, since it typically affects all individuals.

Table 12 Difference Between the Perceived Effect of the Implementation of M.O. No. 35, s. 2014 when Respondents were grouped According to Civil Status

Civil Status	Mean	df	α	Crit x^2	Comp H	Action
Single	2.9090	2	0.05	5.991	2.283	Ho Accepted
Married	2.7764					
Widow/er	2.9889					

Table 12 illustrates the disparity in the perceived impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, based on the respondents' civil status classifications. The application of the Kruskal-Wallis H-test resulted in a computed H value that was lower than the critical chi-square value, indicating acceptance of the hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the perceived effect of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, based on the respondents' civil status. Consequently, it may be interpreted that both married and unmarried fishermen had the same opinion of the impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. The results were corroborated by Rahayu (2020), indicating that the impact of

implementing a regulatory rule significantly transcends an individual's social and economic profile, since it typically affects all individuals. Further, everyone experiences the impact of these regulations, irrespective of their educational background. The findings highlight the importance of inclusive policy-making that considers the diverse perspectives of all stakeholders involved in the fishing community.

Table 13 Difference Between the Perceived Effect of the Implementation of M.O. No. 35, s. 2014 when Respondents were grouped According to Number of Years in Fishing

Number of Years in Fishing	Mean	df	α	Crit x^2	Comp H	Action
Less than 10 years	2.8375	4	0.05	9.488	2.890	Ho Accepted
More than 10 years but less than 15 years	3.0162					
More than 15 years but less than 20 years	2.8040					
More than 20 years but less than 25 years	2.8013					
More than 25 years	2.7556					

Table 13 illustrates the disparity in the perceived impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, categorized by the respondents' years of fishing experience. The application of the Kruskal-Wallis H-test produced a computed H value that was lower than the critical chi-square value, indicating acceptance of the hypothesis asserting no significant difference in the perceived effects of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014, based on the respondents' years of fishing experience. Therefore, we can infer that both novice and seasoned fishermen shared a similar perspective regarding the impact of Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. Alam and Yousuf (2024) corroborated the results, highlighting the impact of an individual's social and economic profile, which typically affects everyone. This suggests that the fishing community perceived the ordinance's implementation uniformly across different experience levels, reflecting a broader consensus. Furthermore, the findings emphasize the need to consider socioeconomic factors when evaluating regulatory measures in similar contexts.

Conclusions

The study surveyed respondents aged 39–48 who were mostly male, elementary/graduate, married, and fishing for over 25 years. The majority favored prohibiting overfishing and fishing during the close season, with a mean of 2.88 verbally interpreted as "observed." The majority favored ensuring sustainable and equitable utilization of coastal and marine resources, with a mean of 3.05 verbally interpreted as "moderate." There was a significant relationship between the level of implementation and the perceived effect of the ordinance. However, no significant difference was found in the

perceived effect when respondents were categorized by age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and years of fishing experience.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were offered:

1. The Municipality of Roxas may continue to implement Municipal Ordinance No. 35, S. 2014. However, the LGU should also conduct training and livelihood programs for fisherman in order to sustain them during leaned months.
2. The Municipality of Roxas through its Municipal Agriculturist Office (MAO) may periodically monitor the implementation of the ordinance particularly those acts which was prohibited by the same. Steeper penalties and prosecution are also recommended for those individuals found violated the provisions of the law.
3. Future researchers were encouraged to benchmark the result of the herein study.
4. A separate study should be conducted in order to determine the veracity of the herein result.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers ensured the anonymity of the research participants and confirmed that consent was freely given for data collection related to this study. All information was stored securely and was destroyed after the study was completed. Confidentiality was strictly maintained.

Additionally, the researchers strictly avoided plagiarism and ensured that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings. The results of this study were used solely for research purposes, adhering to the highest standards of academic integrity. Further, the researchers utilized the use of an AI software for grammar checking and paraphrasing.

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